

EXCELERATE Deliverable 8.2

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1. Executive Summary

This document describes tools for the data manipulation and standard conversions in the rare-disease field. It describes a standard process to make rare disease data more FAIR compliant, services that support FAIRification, and a standardized process to make rare disease genome data comparable. The potential of following the principles of *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data for humans and computers* (FAIR) is recognized in the rare disease community. Therefore, WP8 contributed to the *cross-project rare disease data linkage plan*¹ to leverage documentation of tools for FAIR data manipulation and standard conversions from practical experiences with FAIRification of heterogeneous rare disease data resources.

Seven steps are defined in the FAIRification process: (1) define driving user question(s) for scoping and testing; (2) analyse source data for planning the conversion towards FAIR data; (3) define the semantic model to represent data by ontologies and globally unique identifiers; (4) transform data records using the model of step 3; (5) define metadata to make the data resource more findable, accessible, and reusable; (6) deploy the FAIR data resource through an API that uses the metadata of step 5; (7) apply a query interface and test by executing the driving user questions. Because ontologies fulfill a critical role in step 3 of this workflow, we document the two ontologies that are currently IRDiRC recognized resources and the model that relates the two: the Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology (ORDO), the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) that defined phenotypic abnormalities, and the HPO-ORDO ontological Module (HOOM). Orphanet, the internationally recognized hub for rare disease information, provides HPO annotations of rare diseases defined in ORDO. HOOM qualifies the annotation between a clinical entity and phenotypic abnormalities according to frequency and by integrating the notion of a diagnostic criterion. HOOM was updated and expanded in the context of ELIXIR EXCELERATE WP8. Identifiers are central to interoperability, and this is reflected in the FAIR principles (Figure 2). Going to the level of data elements and data types, FAIR principles require provision of globally unique identifiers, for which this document refers to the URLs that are used in ontologies, the '10 simple rules for persistent identifiers'², Identifiers.org, and an extension of Identifiers.org to add credit and attribution for data providers and databases. For steps 4 and 5 of the FAIRification workflow, Bioschemas is described as an additional means to increase findability for resources that provide a web interface for data records. The RD-Connect platform (<https://platform.rd-connect.eu/>) and Orphanet are also recognized resources to increase findability of rare disease resources. Finally, this document provides background for the standard pipeline that enables comparison of rare disease whole exome and whole genome sequencing data. The pipeline is implemented in the RD-Connect platform. Submission of rare disease genome data via this platform ensures that the data are comparable and stored in the EGA.

¹ https://drive.google.com/open?id=1gVfa3fU-FI-POrkKS_A2JTpK0cTOhAOyFmg5Q2rPhhk

² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28662064>

2. Impact

To produce deliverable 8.2, WP8 contributed to the organisation and execution of the cross-project 'rare disease data linkage plan'. The main aim of this plan is to establish standard procedures, tools, and shareable data models from practical FAIRification of real-life rare disease data with rare disease stakeholders. This resulted in a 'best practice' seven steps to FAIRification (see Appendix). WP8 EXCELERATE activities that support integration and comparison of rare disease data are also described here (bioschemas, identifiers, HOOM). Below we list impact indicators of the deliverable.

D8.2 related activity	Impact indicators
FAIR guiding principles	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Workshops for rare disease data managers contributed to defining the guiding principles as published by Wilkinson and co-authors³ particularly by 'Bring Your Own Data' workshops co-organised between EXCELERATE and rare disease stakeholders. 2. The FAIR guiding principles have been accepted as IRDiRC recognized resource. IRDiRC, the International Rare Disease Research Consortium, is the most important standard-setting organisation in the rare disease domain at a global scale.
FAIRification workflow and supporting FAIR service suite	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The preliminary version of the workflow was the basis for the cross-project 'rare disease data linkage plan' that runs on support from RD-Connect, ELIXIR, ELIXIR-NL, ELIXIR-EXCELERATE, BBMRI-ERIC, BBMRI-ADOPT, BBMRI-NL, Dutch FAIR-development grants (ODEX4All, FAIR-dICT), and contributions from rare disease stakeholders (e.g. the LUMC, Leiden, NL; RadboudUMC on behalf of VASCERN; Rizzoli institute, Bologna Italy)⁴. In turn the rare disease data linkage plan is the basis for organising FAIRification in the European rare disease field. A Global Open FAIR implementation network is in preparation to further support FAIRification in the rare disease community in the context of implementing the European Open Science Cloud for rare disease research. • Outreach through poster and oral presentations

³ The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

⁴ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1qVfa3fU-FI-PORkKS_A2JTpk0cTOhAOvFmg5Q2rPhhk/edit

	<p>at international/European rare disease and bioinformatics events, including the European Conference for Rare diseases and Orphan Drugs (Edinburgh, 2016⁵; Vienna, 2018⁶), the IRDiRC conference (Paris, 2017)⁷, RD-ACTION Workshop Co-hosted by DG SANTE: Using standards and embedding good practices to promote interoperable data sharing in ERNs (Brussels, 2017)⁸, RD-Connect annual meetings (2015, 2016, 2017, 2018)⁹, E-Rare workshop (Berlin, 2017)¹⁰, European Conference of Human Genetics (2016, 2017)¹¹, Semantic Web Application and Tools for Health Care and Life Science (2016, 2017)¹², ISMB/ECCB (Prague, 2017)¹³, also presented as ELIXIR webinar¹⁴.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Book chapter in “Rare Diseases Epidemiology: Update and Overview”, Eds. Posada de la Paz M., Taruscio D., Groft S.¹⁵ • Training events, particularly the BYOD associated with the annual summer school for rare disease registry managers (Rome, 2015-2018)¹⁶, and the ‘Sample & Data Banking’ Course, Bologna, 2017 & 2018¹⁷. • Grant proposals in the rare disease domain that include FAIRification, particularly the European Joint Program-COFUND (SC1-BHC-04-2018, accepted).
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⁵ https://www.apmar.it/documenti/eventi/Eurordis_2016_-_ecrd-programme.compressed.pdf

⁶ http://download2.eurordis.org.s3.amazonaws.com/ecrd/ECRD_2018/Poster%20PDFs/theme%206/P159.pdf

⁷ <https://www.slideshare.net/MarcoRoos/rare-disease-data-linkage-plan-2017-irdirc-2017-presentation>

⁸ <http://www.rd-action.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Final-Agenda-for-Workshop-Using-standards-and-embedding-good-practices-to-promote-interoperable-data-sharing-in-ERNs.docx>; <http://www.rd-action.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/Making-FAIR-Data-in-the-ERN-framework-Roos-and-Carta-RD-ACTION-Workshop-27.4.17.pdf>

⁹ <https://rd-connect.eu/?s=annual>

¹⁰ <http://www.erare.eu/download/file/fid/2424>

¹¹ Boosting genotype-phenotype and translational research on rare diseases by establishing Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable data resources through data linking technologies. Enckevort, D., v.; Carta, C.; Thompson, R.; Thompson, M.; Ehrhart, F.; Kaliyaperumal, R.; Sernadela, P.; Reihs, R.; Jacobsen, A.; da Silva Santos, L., O., B.; Wilkinson, M., D.; Muller, H.; Oliviera, J., L.; Evelo, C., T.; Taruscio, D.; 't Hoen, P., A.; and Roos, M. In ESHG 2017, 2017.

¹² http://www.swat4ls.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/SWAT4LS-2017_paper_27.pdf

¹³ <https://www.iscb.org/uploaded/css/222/38421.pdf>; <https://www.iscb.org/ismbeccb2017-program/elixir-special-track>;

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MSasvoa0dV4>

¹⁵ Roos M., López Martin E., Wilkinson M.D. (2017) Preparing Data at the Source to Foster Interoperability across Rare Disease Resources. In: Posada de la Paz M., Taruscio D., Groft S. (eds) Rare Diseases Epidemiology: Update and Overview. Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology, vol 1031. Springer, Cham, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-67144-4_9

¹⁶ 2015: <http://old.iss.it/cnmr/?lang=1&id=2662&tipo=3>, 2016: <http://old.iss.it/cnmr/?lang=1&id=2662&tipo=3>, 2017: <http://old.iss.it/cnmr/?id=2739&tipo=3>, 2018: <https://cnmr.iss.it/2018/03/23/news-eventi/>

¹⁷ <http://www.bbmri-eric.eu/news-events/sample-data-banking-course/>

3. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Deliver world-leading data services for academia and industry: Demonstrate, in partnership with the Rare Disease community, how aligned ELIXIR resources enable research, avoid fragmentation and support the development of sustainability models for resources created by the community research projects	X	

4. Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

5. Adjustments made

The deliverable the result of a highly collaborative rare disease data linkage plan. To ensure a grass-roots process, developing tools for the data manipulation and standard conversions in the rare-disease field required intensive interdisciplinary collaboration with stakeholders, as well as their investments.

6. Background information

Background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of action (DoA) is included here for reference.

Work package number	8	Start date or starting event:	month 1
Work package title	Use Case C: ELIXIR infrastructure for Rare Disease research		
Lead	Marco Roos, 6 - LUMC (LTP to NBIC) - NL; Ivo Gut 8 - CRG - ES.		
Participant number and person months per participant 4 - UNIMAN 6.00; 6 - NBIC 0.00; LUMC (LTP) 6.00; 8 - CRG 38.40 ; 9 - CIPF 2.66; 12 - BSC 10.00; 22 - NTNU 12.00; 26 - CNRS 12.00; 30 - CNR 6.39; 32 - UL 15.00; 38 - DTU 12.00; 48 - FPS 4.54.			
WP8 - Use Case C: ELIXIR infrastructure for Rare Disease research [Months: 1-48] CRG, UNIMAN, NBIC, CIPF, BSC, NTNU, CNRS, CNR, UL, DTU, FPS The International Rare Diseases Research Consortium (http://www.irdirc.org) established the ambitious goal of developing 200 new therapies by 2020. ELIXIR as a			

whole and in particular this Work Package is aligned with this effort. The overall objective of this Work Package (WP) is to address the needs of the rare diseases community through the instantiation of the ELIXIR resources described in WP1-5. These resources do not constitute a replacement of the current research projects organized around the rare diseases area. Indeed the aim is to empower them and to help in the sustainability of the resources created by these projects in the long term.

This WP is organised around the actors that play a major role on the development of these new therapies. These actors are the main users of the ELIXIR infrastructure: data generators and curators (usually personnel working in hospitals, genomics-based companies, and members of large research consortia), researchers (bioinformaticians, geneticists, and clinical doctors), diagnosis companies, CROs (usually SMEs), and the pharmaceutical industry among others.

Objectives

WP8 aims to empower actors involved in the development of new rare disease therapies through the execution of the following specific objectives:

- Build the ELIXIR registry of data resources and analysis tools critical for the development of the rare disease research. (Task 8.1)
Continuous monitoring of resources and tools in Rare-diseases.
Implementation of a system for the generation of datasets adequate for the assessment of methods in the area of rare-diseases.
Implementation of the ELIXIR rare-disease portfolio in the ELIXIR registry.
- Implementation of a technical framework for the comparison and standardization of services useful for the rare-disease communities. (Task 8.2)
- Collaboration with the rare-disease communities for the organization of training courses, workshops and jamborees. (Task 8.3)

Work Package Leads: Ivo Gut (CRG - ES), Marco Roos (LUMC - NL)

Description of work and role of partners

Task 8.1: The ELIXIR portfolio of data resources developed in collaboration with the rare diseases communities. (69.4PM)

Subtask 8.1.1 Monitoring of resources and tools. (25.4PM)

There is a wide range of data resources and analysis methods used in the rare-disease area. Many of those resources are provided by ELIXIR Nodes, for example the European Genome-Phenome archive (EGA) currently stores data from major research initiatives in rare diseases like the RD-connect project. In this subtask we will review the current data resources and evaluate their usability and potential impact on the rare disease community. An important aspect of the evaluation will be the security of the data that is a key aspect in rare disease domain given the low frequency of the associated genomic variants in the population.

One critical aspect of the development of the registry is to engage the different communities in the submission and rating of the tools. In this task we will work together with representatives of the major projects in the field of rare-diseases to create a customized portfolio of ELIXIR tools and services devoted to assist them in the development of these new therapies. As an example we will ask for proposals of tools that serve to interpret the effect of genomics variants on a group of patients that belong to the same family. We strongly believe that this link between the end- users and the tools developers will help ELIXIR to understand better the problems that are actually facing the main actors in the rare diseases research and hence to better solutions.

The final outcome of this task will be the ELIXIR data resources and analysis tools useful to the rare disease communities.

Partners: NO, ES, SI, IT, NL

Subtask 8.1.2: Creation of reference datasets adequate for the specific assessment of methods and standards in the area of rare-diseases. (30PM)

While the creation of these tools should stay as a priority for researchers, large scale projects, SMEs and the industry increasingly need access to benchmarked methods on which to build their analysis strategies.

The evaluation of the methods requires the adequate selection of the datasets and benchmarking strategies. The systems for the selection of the datasets for the benchmarking have to be fast and effective to enable the continuous evaluation

of the methods, as described in WP2. We will collaborate with the ELIXIR benchmarking strategy (WP2) to build the appropriate strategies for the selection of the datasets (subtask 8.1.1 above) and with the rare- disease communities to implement the adequate quality reporting standards. Moreover we will integrate these pipelines in the ELIXIR benchmarking framework (WP2) to continuously monitor the selected methods with the newly generated datasets.

Partners: ES, DK, IT, FR, SI, UK

Subtask 8.1.3 Implementation of the ELIXIR rare-disease portfolio in the ELIXIR registry. (14PM)

The ELIXIR registry will be a reference for the research community (WP1), as it will reflect the quality and the real-time status of the services included on it. This registry will act as a one-stop shop for services provided by ELIXIR. The goal is to allow users from the different countries, communities and projects to discover which are the tools available at a given time, with the associated information about the community based rating (see WP2), instructions for correct use and associated examples We will encourage tools developers to adopt the EDAM standard to describe their tools and to share several metrics about the performance and usage of these of the tools (see description in WP1).

Those services promoted as relevant by the end-users will be listed in a special section in the ELIXIR registry.

Partners: DK, ES, FR.

Task 8.2: Standardisation of rare disease services in collaboration with the rare disease communities. (36PM)

The ecosystem of RD services will inevitably be a combination of distributed and

centralized resources, because of the sheer number of rare diseases and rare disease organisations, as well as legal and ethical constraints between countries and communities. At the same time, because of the low frequency in the population, combining data across patient registries, biobanks, and -omics databases is the single most important way of getting new insights towards new treatments.

One of the most recurrent issues when attempting to perform research across resources is the lack of standards or the poor adoption of existing standards by rare disease stakeholders. Rare disease standards concern different types of data including genomic and phenotypic characteristics, causative genetic variation status, quality criteria, analysis protocols, supporting evidence and follow-up indicators. These problems will be analysed in workshops including experts in semantic web, linked data technologies and rare-disease experts (see previous experiences and proposal in “Bring Your Own Data (BYOD) bootcamps”, in WP5). The initial experience with this methodology (see 61) is that a critical bottleneck is the identification of the most appropriate terms and identifiers to annotate data for cross- resource questions. Based on this experience we aim to address two major 'white spots' in the available infrastructure for Rare-diseases: (i) the current infrastructure of the rare disease platform: RD-Connect, does not contain backbone services for functional interlinking, (ii) a majority of rare disease sources are not equipped to provide data, metadata, and data updates using appropriate standard procedures. To address these needs we will work together with WP5, the rare-disease communities and the RD-Connect project to (i) deploy and test the services and guidelines for standardization 'at the source', (ii) provide standardized interfaces that Rare-disease communities can work with from a central location, (iii) build capacity in the rare disease community by enabling them to work with these services themselves.

Partners: FR, ES, DK, NL.

Task 8.3: Training workshops targeting different user communities. (32PM)

In this task training workshops and courses will be delivered, in partnership with WP11 “EXCELERATE Training Programme”. The training will be approached from two sides. First, in collaboration with the Train the Researcher task in WP11 we will train rare diseases' researchers in the use of relevant tools, standards and infrastructure produced by ELIXIR. Second, we will run “feedback workshops” in which those who are developing the methods will be exposed directly to problems faced by the rare disease community. These userthons will help to shape the ELIXIR portfolio.

The direct collaboration with WP11 Train the Researcher will ensure that researchers are trained to a high standard in state-of-the-art analysis techniques for rare disease data and that innovative training approaches developed in this task are applied elsewhere in ELIXIR.

Partners: UK, SI, NL.

Appendix 1: Tools, expertise and procedure for FAIRification of rare disease resources

A1.1. Introduction

Also in the rare disease community, the concept of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data for humans and computers (FAIR principles) is acknowledged for its potential to facilitate analysis across sparse and distributed rare disease data, and to perform analysis between sample collections in biobanks, patient and disease information in registries, information hubs such as Orphanet, and molecule-level resources such as variant databases. The FAIR principles originate from a [Lorentz center workshop](#) in 2014 co-organized by LUMC. Thereafter an enormous uptake of FAIR data principles has taken place. It has been adopted by ELIXIR and organizations such as Force11, NIH Data Commons, the Research Data Alliance, as well as with publishers and in European scientific policy (European Open Science Cloud - [EOSC](#)) and global politics ([G20 Summit 2016](#)).

In March 2016, a coalition of stakeholders published "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship" in [Nature Scientific Data](#), detailing a concise set of principles and requirements for data and the supporting data infrastructure to be FAIR. These guiding principles are widely considered to be the reference definition of FAIR. In the rare disease community they were recently recognized by the International Rare Disease Research Consortium (IRDIRC). The FAIR principles do not prescribe any specific implementation or standard, which occasionally has led to disagreement about what it means to be FAIR and what data resources are justified to carry the label "FAIR". In answer to this, a follow-up [paper](#) was published to elucidate some aspects of the original paper and a working group was started to determine FAIR [metrics](#). Simultaneously and in line with its focus on interoperability, the Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences that represents ELIXIR-NL has coordinated the collaborative development of a suite of tools and standards that serves the dual purpose of being a reference platform (demonstrating what a FAIR data infrastructure could look like) and a set of reusable components which may be adopted (whole or in part) by any infrastructure that would like to adopt FAIR principles (or certain aspects of FAIR). WP8 has contributed to this development in the context of the delivering tools for data manipulation and standard conversions in the rare-disease field (this deliverable). With additional support from ELIXIR, RD-Connect, and others, ELIXIR-NL members LUMC and UMCG led the development of the cross-project 'rare disease data linkage plan'. Working within this plan allowed us to leverage this EXCELERATE deliverable from practical experience with FAIRification of rare disease data.

Below we describe existing FAIR procedures, expertise and tools, which are based on our experiences from FAIRifying various rare disease resources, such as registries for Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD), vascular anomalies (VA), and Osteogenesis imperfecta (OI). We will use the term 'data steward' for the person(s) who contribute to increasing the long-term reusability of data, here by making data comply with the FAIR guiding principles ('FAIR data stewards'). Tools and data manipulation to make

record-level data linkable by standards that can operate globally and across different types of data sources received a significant amount of attention, considering that this is the largest hurdle for scaling up to efficient, high quality analysis over distributed rare disease data resources. The FAIRification projects under the 'rare disease data linkage plan' were all interdisciplinary collaborations between FAIR experts and managers of a rare disease data source. A prerequisite for knowledge transfer was that a data steward working on the side of the domain expert is committed to each case.

The documentation of the FAIRification steps is augmented by documentation of auxiliary tools for manipulation and standard conversion of rare disease data: the interconnection of the Orphanet Disease Ontology and the Human Phenotype Ontology, Identifiers.org, bioschemas, and the standard pipeline for making rare disease genome data comparable which is available from the RD-Connect genome-phenome analysis platform.

A1.2. The 7-step FAIRification process, tools and expertise

Workflow

A workflow describing the FAIRification process of rare disease resources can be seen in Figure 1. The workflow has been developed based on our experience from previous FAIRification projects and 'Bring Your Own Data' (BYOD) events. This workflow assumes a "non-FAIR" dataset as input and in subsequent steps progressively adds FAIR properties making it "more FAIR". The steps described in this workflow are not always followed in strict sequential order. Each case is different and practical constraints or new insights sometimes lead to a different order of execution and some steps are often visited multiple times.

Figure 1: FAIRification workflow. Boxes indicate the seven steps: the order is not strict and can be iterative. The bullet points indicate typical aspects of each FAIRification step in practice.

Step 1: Define driving user question(s)

The first step is to define driving user question(s). These are defined in order to focus the FAIRification to a subset of the data elements. The data elements should be carefully studied and selected to make sure that the driving user questions can be answered. The driving user questions themselves should be defined together with the domain experts.

Step 2: Pre-FAIRification analysis

To be Findable:

- F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
- F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
- F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
- F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource

To be Accessible:

- A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
- A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available

To be Interoperable:

- I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data

To be Reusable:

- R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes

- | |
|---|
| R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards |
|---|

Figure 2: The FAIR guiding principles, reproduced from Wilkinson *et al.*, box 2¹

The second step is to prepare for subsequent FAIRification steps by establishing the current 'FAIRness' of the dataset. This process may include: (1) investigating the source dataset in whatever form(s) it is available and check whether both the data representation (format) and the meaning of the dataset are clear; (2) Checking whether the data already contains any FAIR features, such as persistent unique identifiers for data elements (F1) or rich metadata and provenance descriptions (R1-R1.3, Figure 2)¹⁸. (3) Checking whether the dataset contains the data items needed to answer the driving user question(s).

The pre-FAIRification analysis step includes an assessment of the cost of FAIRification, which depends on factors such as the complexity of the data set (the number of different types of data elements), similarity to previously FAIRified data (for reuse), and the expertise available in the FAIRification team (e.g. how much a domain expert can contribute to data and metadata modelling). When the cost of FAIRification of an entire data set is deemed too high, the data set can be segmented to prioritize and plan the in-depth FAIRification of the segments. Alternatively, some simple first steps towards more FAIR data can be considered, such as recoding diseases and phenotypes into [Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology \(ORDO\)](#) and [Human Phenotype Ontology \(HPO\)](#) identifiers. Tools such as SORTA can assist in this step¹⁹.

Step 3: Define semantic model

The third step is to generate a semantic model of the data. Here, first a conceptual model is created that serves as a precursor for the final FAIR data model. It lists the main concepts and relationships between data elements that are specified in the driving user questions or that are otherwise considered to be important to represent the knowledge domain. This model may be defined at a high level of abstraction and can omit detailed data (element) descriptions, as those will be specified in the next step.

The structure of the data resource should be studied with regard to the selected driving user question(s) to be able to create an initial conceptual model defining the relationships between the relevant data elements. As a thorough knowledge of the domain is necessary, domain specialists should be involved in this process. In our experience, the (abstract) conceptual model is a good vehicle for discussion with domain experts. We note two particular advantages. (1) It helps the data steward to obtain the required domain knowledge from domain experts. (2) It enables domain experts to contribute to the FAIR data model without getting stuck in implementation details (for example details related to the instance model or its implementation in RDF, see below). Not all of the concepts in the conceptual model will necessarily be used in the final FAIR

¹⁸ For a full list of FAIR principles, see this Nature Scientific Data paper: <http://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

¹⁹ Pang, C. et al., SORTA: a system for ontology-based re-coding and technical annotation of biomedical phenotype data. Database, 2015, DOI: 10.1093/database/bav089

data model and their purpose is just to support the discussions or clarify the importance of a concept or relationship in the model.

Ontology terms are necessary to exactly define the concepts in the conceptual model, in a machine readable and linkable way. Ontologies are typically field specific and often even goal specific, so it can be very difficult to decide which term from which ontology should be used. When terms appear to be missing from current ontologies, we first recommend an exhaustive search with help of ontology experts. Terms used in human narrative do not always match directly with the ontological representation of the term. If the search is still unsuccessful, new ontology terms could be defined and added to existing ontologies or new ontologies could be developed. This is a very time consuming process that should be undertaken with a team of experts from both the domain of the study as well as in consultation with ontology experts.

There are multiple search engines available specifically to search for ontologies, such as the [Ontology Lookup service \(OLS\)](#) and [BioPortal](#). To find the most appropriate ontology term it is important to minimize the chance that potentially relevant terms are missed. In order to be able to do this, it is essential to know how to search and to know the technical details of the search engines of the ontology repositories. This is, however, in our experience not completely clear from both search engines. The OLS provides [technical details](#) on the functionality of the search engine, but this is a very technical description that is only understandable for skilled users. At this time and in our experience, performing good searches is a very time demanding task for data stewards. It demands good searching skills and experience with building application ontologies to make optimal ontology choices. The ranking of the ontologies in the search results does not necessarily represent how application ontologists select their concepts. Therefore, we make the following two recommendations for rare disease data stewards: (i) involve an experienced developer of application ontologies, for instance by contacting the cross-project 'rare disease FAIR data task force' (previously named 'rare disease linked data and ontology task force')²⁰, (ii) version application models and improve them with expert help over time, so that a model can evolve from a first provisional model to a mature model reviewed by experts. A useful feature of ontologies and linked data (RDF) is that it is relatively easy to improve models and reconnect data with an improved model or even multiple models. We further recommend to *not* choose the first ontology in the list provided by ontology search tools by definition, but check the usability license, usage statistics, update activity, if the ontology contains properties (this serves data integration), and if a general ontological framework is used (such as OBO Foundry). The guidelines by the Pistoia alliance also provide useful recommendations²¹.

Support for rare disease data stewards for this critical step of FAIRification could be improved. We think that the functionality of ontology search tools could be improved, also because data stewards are a growing class of potential users of these tools. FAIRsharing.org has a lot of potential for supporting the modelling step of FAIRification. Preferably, data stewards first search and reuse application models (application ontologies) that were used in previous FAIRifications or are commonly used in FAIR data

²⁰fair-rd-info@elixir-europe.org

²¹<https://pistoiaalliance.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/PUB/pages/43089942/Ontologies+Guidelines+for+Best+Practice>

repositories like the ELIXIR recommended repositories. FAIRsharing.org offers features to store and search such application models. However, their numbers are still small, and FAIRsharing.org is not yet supporting this step of FAIRification specifically. FAIR data stewards can be further assisted when the most commonly used ontologies are pre-loaded in the FAIRifier tool²², such that data stewards will be able to easily find ontology terms for the concepts that are frequently used within the biomedical and clinical domain. We would recommend to include data models in the FAIRifier tool, such that for the most frequently used concepts a model is readily available. Through repeated practical application of the FAIRification workflow, more ontologies and more tutorials/manuals can be recognized by the rare disease community to support data stewards in cases where the ontologies in the FAIRifier do not provide appropriate terms. When ontology search tools follow these recommendations in their ranking, users will be able to search for ontology terms themselves.

The results from the conceptual model and the ontology/data model search efforts are combined into a single, detailed model, which we refer to as the instance model, because in contrast to the conceptual model, it distinguishes between the data items (instances) and their types (classes). A fully specified instance model provides a template to transform data records from their original data representation to a FAIR data representation, such as an RDF graph (see the next step: FAIRifier). The instance model is an exact representation of the data that will be included in the FAIR data distribution of the source dataset. We recommend using RDF for the purpose of making data linkable at record-level²³.

Recommendations for what to include or exclude in a data model: Include (1) prioritized concepts that are required to answer the driving user questions; (2) concepts and relationships that are required to logically link other included concepts and relationships; (3) any relevant data item contained in the source dataset; (4) when reusing an existing (suitable!) data model, include relevant data items suggested or required by that data model. Exclude any data item that can only be obtained by extrapolation or inference from the source dataset. These need to be defined by domain experts, ideally using some consensus approach and captured by (new) ontological definitions. Including items that were not checked by domain experts to truly reflect the implied meaning of the data should be avoided.

Step 4: Transform data records

In the fourth step a FAIR representation of the data records is instantiated. The output will be an RDF representation of the data records which follows the structure of the instance data model. This RDF, together with the RDF of the metadata (previous section) forms the basis of the semantic, machine readable representation of the dataset conform the FAIR principles.

²² <https://www.dtls.nl/fair-data/find-fair-data-tools/> and EXCELERATE milestone M8.4

²³ RDF, Resource Description Framework, reuses web technologies that have proven to scale massively (i.e. the world-wide web). It provides a backbone for interoperability that functions globally and across domain boundaries. RDF does not specify a domain model directly, but domain models for any topic can be defined in RDF, as well as mappings between models. We recommend using RDF for interoperability and exchange, not for compute-intensive analyses. Conversion into a format appropriate for the analysis is recommended (e.g. an R dataframe).

There are different options to create the RDF data representation, but typically all methods consist of a way to create some kind of template representation of the data model: i.e. an RDF document with variables or placeholders in the place of the actual values from the source dataset. An iterative process then will instantiate a copy of the RDF document where the variables are filled in: each time with a different record from the source dataset. Traditionally, custom programming scripts were used for this purpose, but for rare disease resources we recommend the FAIRifier tool developed by Dutch Techcentre for Lifesciences (DTL)²⁴. The FAIRifier builds on the open source OpenRefine software with RDF plugin. OpenRefine is a tool for wrangling and cleaning tabular data, which includes operations such as cleaning, augmenting and transforming. We should mention here that conversion of all data to RDF is not always necessary or even desirable. The RDF data representation can also be used to convert queries to some other internal data format. From the perspective of the querying agent there is no difference.

A typical workflow using the FAIRifier looks like this: (1) Load the dataset in its original representation. (2) Check header and cell values: fix values that were loaded incorrectly (e.g. wrong datatype interpretation). (3) Map column values to vocabulary URLs where needed (as specified by instance data model). (4) Transcribe instance data model using the built-in model editor. (5) Instantiate and export RDF (all data records). (6) Validate RDF. (7) deploy RDF to FAIR Data Point (next step).

Note that steps 2 to 6 can be performed iteratively and therefore it is possible to work on one part of the dataset first (a subset of columns and/or a small part of the instance model). The FAIRifier keeps a record of every transformation action from the user, which helps with provenance (who changed what) and also makes the FAIRification reproducible: all (or some) steps can be rolled back or applied again to the same source dataset, or (under certain conditions) to a different source dataset. Moreover, it is possible to extract the transcribed data model (step 4), allowing it to be stored and shared separately from the data. The FAIRifier currently has rudimentary support for sharing data models in a kind of shared data model registry, such as via FAIRsharing.org. As the data model does not contain the data itself, it may in most cases be shared freely, thus supporting model reuse, which in turn reduces modeling effort and increases interoperability for other datasets of a similar type. It is future work to extend application model sharing facilities for FAIR data stewards.

The FAIRifier offers different ways to perform similar transformations, making it a flexible, but also a somewhat technically challenging tool, especially for people without a technical / ICT background and it is in its current state likely not usable for a typical biomedical researcher. This should be mitigated in the future by embedding FAIRification in existing data (capture) tools, further development of the FAIR tools ecosystem, and increased availability of reusable FAIR data models and training for end-users.

Additionally, if the data source provides a web interface to its data records, the original HTML representation of the data records can be enhanced for Findability and lightweight Interoperability by embedding Schema.org markup according to the

²⁴ <https://www.dtls.nl/fair-data/find-fair-data-tools/>

appropriate Bioschemas profile for the data type. See Bioschemas section below for more details.

Step 5: Define metadata

Just like the data records, the dataset metadata (data describing the dataset) should also be described in a machine-readable format (RDF). There are different standards that can be used to describe the metadata. We recommend using the DTL Metadata Editor (a free online tool; more information on the DTL FAIR tool [site](#)¹), which uses the DCAT metadata standard. In our experience this is a very helpful tool for creating the metadata, but it does need further development. This provides rich metadata about the dataset.

Good metadata increases the potential to make a resource more findable. We mention two additional mechanisms to increase findability of rare disease resources. First, we recommend to register your resource in an IRDiRC recognized platform (<http://www.irdirc.org/research/irdirc-recognized-resources/>). The RD-Connect platform (<https://platform.rd-connect.eu/>), for instance, is a portal to the rare disease sample catalogue and the biobank and registry finder. Orphanet also indexes several rare disease resources. Secondly, to enable indexing of the dataset by general purpose web search engines such as Google, we recommend including Schema.org markup according to the Bioschemas [DataCatalog](#) and [Dataset](#) profiles.

Step 6: Deploy FAIR data resource

The set of metadata captured using the Metadata Editor is available for human and machine consumption through different interfaces. These interfaces are provided by the FAIR Data Point (FDP) software component from the DTL FAIR data tool suite¹. The former consists of a simple web interface providing links to the relevant layers of metadata provided by the FDP. The latter consists of a machine readable RDF document that is returned when the web interface is approached by a machine (using the appropriate standardized Accept-header mechanism). This might for example be a search engine for FAIR data resources that is indexing FAIR resources (similar to how Google and other search engines index websites).

Step 7: Query interface or user app

In the seventh step, the driving research question from step 1 is answered. Because the data now is available in RDF format, SPARQL queries are provisionally used to retrieve the data required to answer this question. We note that while it is beyond the scope of the general FAIRification process described here, we recommend incorporating the FAIR data point API into the local infrastructure to enable distributed cross-resource analysis. SPARQL is useful for testing, but other mechanisms for accessing underlying linkable data can also be enabled via the FAIR data point. In the context of the rare disease data linkage plan, the development of 'FAIR service-oriented architecture' that tool developers can deploy is further investigated.

A1.3 Recognised models for rare diseases, phenotype abnormalities, and relationships between concepts

The seven steps above describe a general workflow towards a (more) FAIR rare disease data resource. Ontologies fulfill an important role for interoperability in step 3 of this

workflow. Resources are more interoperable when the same ontologies are used to describe the same type of data. Henceforth, interoperability is served when a community converges to using the same, high-quality ontologies. At this time in the rare disease community, two ontologies are IRDiRC recognized resources: the Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology (ORDO) and the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO). Recently, the relations between ORDO diseases and HPO phenotypes have also been defined and curated. We recommend to apply these ontologies as a backbone for interoperability in the rare disease domain. This is straightforward if the data contain rare diseases or phenotypes. Otherwise, we recommend to consider adding either or both during FAIRification. In this section we elaborate on these two ontologies and their interrelation.

Orphanet provides a clinical description of rare diseases using a set of clinical signs and symptoms (phenotypic abnormalities). This description, based on cases published in biomedical literature, uses the phenotypic abnormalities referenced in the HPO. Each phenotypic abnormality is presented by order of frequency of occurrence in the patient population. The frequency in the patients' population can be:

- always present: 100%
- very frequent: 99%-80%
- frequent: 79%-30%
- occasional: 29%-5%
- rare: 4%-1%

The phenotypic abnormality can be defined as one of the following :

- Pathognomonic sign : A sign whose presence indicates that a particular disease is present beyond any doubt. The absence of this sign does not exclude the possibility of the presence of the disease, but the presence of the pathognomonic sign affirms it with certainty.
- Diagnostic criterion : phenotypic abnormalities noted as « diagnostic criterion » are those included in established sets of criteria to establish the diagnosis of a particular disease having been published in a peer-reviewed journal.
- Exclusion criterion : phenotypic abnormalities noted as « exclusion criterion » are those that are always absent in a particular disease and therefore exclude its diagnosis.

Currently, in the Orphanet database, we have annotated 3224 disorders, using 5693 HPO terms, providing 67896 HPO annotations. On the Orphanet website, the information is displayed in the “Clinical Signs and Symptoms” part of the site as shown in Figure 3.

The screenshot shows the Orphanet website interface for the entry 'Rett syndrome' (ORPHA:778). The page includes a search bar, navigation links, and a list of clinical signs and symptoms categorized by frequency. The 'Very frequent' category lists the following symptoms with their corresponding HPO IDs:

Very frequent	
Abnormality of movement	HP:0100022
Abnormality of the skull	HP:0000929
Apraxia	HP:0002186
Behavioral abnormality	HP:0000708
Dysphasia	HP:0002357
EEG abnormality	HP:0002353
Intellectual disability, severe	HP:0010864
Microcephaly	HP:0000252
Seizures	HP:0001250
Stereotypy	HP:0000733

Figure 3: phenotypic information on Rett syndrome.

Orphanet provides also the Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology (ORDO). This structured vocabulary, recognized by IRDiRC, captures relationships between rare diseases, genes and other relevant features. It forms a useful backbone for the computational analysis of information linked to rare diseases in Orphanet and the many distributed rare disease data resources.

ORDO is derived from the Orphanet database (www.orpha.net). It integrates a nosology (classification of rare diseases), relationships (gene-disease relations, epidemiological data) and connections with other terminologies (MeSH, UMLS, MedDRA), databases (OMIM, UniProtKB, HGNC, Ensembl, Reactome, IUPHAR, GenAtlas) or classifications (ICD10).

ORDO is available on Bioportal, EBI's OLS tools and downloadable from www.orphadata.org. In order to ease query processing and support Interoperability as part of the FAIR approach, Orphanet provides also a Sparql endpoint and queries sample: <http://www.orphadata.org/cgi-bin/inc/sparql.inc.php>. ORDO is updated twice a year, is available in English and French and will be extended to further languages. The current version is 2.6: <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ORDO>.

HOOM : HPO-ORDO ontological Module

Orphanet provides phenotypic annotations of the rare diseases in the Orphanet nomenclature using the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO). HOOM is a module that qualifies the annotation between a clinical entity and phenotypic abnormalities according to frequency and by integrating the notion of a diagnostic criterion. In ORDO a clinical entity is either a group of rare disorders, a rare disorder or a subtype of disorder. The « phenomes » branch of ORDO has been refactored as a logical import of HPO, and the HPO-ORDO phenotype disease-annotations have been provided in a series of triples in OBAN format in which associations, frequency and provenance are modeled (Figure 4).

Figure 4: HOOM model.

HOOM is provided as an OWL (Ontologies Web Languages) file, using OBAN, the ORDO, and HPO ontological models. It follows the update timeline of ORDO (twice a year), and is embedded in the Orphanet SPARQL Endpoint with ORDO and could be used in a federated queries approach.

In the SPARQL endpoint it is possible to check the amount of annotations provided (Figure 5).

Figure 5: SPARQL query counting associated annotations between disorders and HPO terms.

Through SPARQL queries one can obtain any phenotypic annotations with frequencies for a specific disorder concept (Figure 6).

```
#select DISTINCT ?association ?Property ?value ?date ?label ?comment
select DISTINCT ?association ?label ?comment
where {
?association owl:equivalentClass ?collection .
?collection owl:intersectionOf ?list .
?list rdf:rest*/rdf:first ?item .
?item owl:someValuesFrom <http://www.orpha.net/ORDO/Orphanet_558>
OPTIONAL {
?association owl:equivalentClass ?node .
?node owl:intersectionOf ?list2 .
?list2 rdf:rest*/rdf:first ?item2 .
?item2 owl:onProperty ?Property. OPTIONAL {
?item2 owl:someValuesFrom ?value . OPTIONAL {?value rdfs:label ?label} . OPTIONAL {?value rdfs:comment ?comment}
}
}
OPTIONAL {
```

association	label	
http://www.semanticweb.org/ontology/HOOM#56420_Asso	"HP:0000275"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>	"Objective measurement of the upper facial width is made with sprea
http://www.semanticweb.org/ontology/HOOM#56420_Asso	"Narrow face"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>	"Objective measurement of the upper facial width is made with sprea
http://www.semanticweb.org/ontology/HOOM#56420_Asso	"Orphanet:558"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>	"Marfan syndrome"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>
http://www.semanticweb.org/ontology/HOOM#56420_Asso	"Marfan syndrome"8en	"Marfan syndrome"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>
http://www.semanticweb.org/ontology/HOOM#56420_Asso	"Frequent"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>	"The phenotypic abnormality is present in 30 to 79% of cases"^^<http
http://www.semanticweb.org/ontology/HOOM#56420_Asso		
http://www.semanticweb.org/ontology/HOOM#56421_Asso	"Orphanet:558"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>	"Marfan syndrome"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>
http://www.semanticweb.org/ontology/HOOM#56421_Asso	"Marfan syndrome"8en	"Marfan syndrome"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>
http://www.semanticweb.org/ontology/HOOM#56421_Asso	"Occasional"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>	"The phenotypic abnormality is present in 5 to 29% of cases"^^<http
http://www.semanticweb.org/ontology/HOOM#56421_Asso	"HP:0001252"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string>	

Figure 6: SPARQL query to obtain phenotypic annotations about Marfan disease ORPHA:558.

Orphanet also provides a docker image of a blazegraph triplestore of both ORDO and HOOM (Figure 7).

HOOM-ORDO Docker Image

A Blazegraph Docker image (356M) which embed HOOM and ORDO ontologies is available [here](#) in order to play local queries.

Blazegraph is a standards-based, high-performance, scalable, open-source graph database and written entirely in Java.

For more information, see [Blazegraph](#) website.

A Linux host is **prerequisite**, with Docker machine installed.

More informations about running the HOOM-ORDO container are available in the [userguide](#).

Figure 7: availability of HOOM and ORDO docker image.

HOOM provides extra possibilities for researchers, pharmaceutical companies and others wishing to co-analyse rare and common disease phenotype associations, or re-use the integrated ontologies in genomic variants repositories or match-making tools. Integrated into SPARQL endpoint, HOOM increases the machine readability of the annotations provided by Orphanet on our website.

The HOOM modelisation has been developed in the context of HIPBI-RD project (receiving funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the ERA-NET Cofund action N° 643578) and was updated and expanded in the context of ELIXIR EXCELERATE WP8.

A1.4. Identifiers

Identifiers are central to interoperability, and this is reflected in the FAIR principles (Figure 2). The detailed 'Findability' principle 'F1' states that metadata and data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier, while 'F3' indicates that metadata clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the data it describes. Access to metadata through standardised protocols is highlighted in 'Accessibility' principle 'A1'. Hence, the visibility and discoverability of data on the web, accomplished through metadata, and presented through their identifiers, is a key strategy in promoting FAIRness. This implies that scientific data consistently uses unique, standards-compliant persistent identifiers, typically manifested as URI.

Existing ontologies that are used in a semantic data model provide globally unique identifiers for the classes, properties, etcetera, in the form of URLs. The FAIRifier helps connect these to the values in a data set. Ontologies are registered in NCBO's BioPortal²⁵, EBI's Ontology Lookup Service²⁶, and Identifiers.org, services that will exchange and synchronise their information. For machine-readability, it is advisable to consider for all values in a data set if they can be represented by a globally unique, persistent identifier. For example, if an observation of symptoms can be represented by an HPO identifier, a differentially expressed gene by an ENSEMBL ID, etcetera. Enumerated values are often defined by a standard somewhere, or there is an authoritative data provider that provides trusted identifiers. An example from the rare disease community are the IRDiRC recognized OrphaCodes to denote rare diseases in a data set.

Ideally, identifiers come from an authoritative source that also provides a URL linked to an ontology. However, this is not always the case, which makes it non-trivial to find and choose a good identifier for all values. In general, we recommend that the process by which identifiers are generated complies with the '10 simple rules'²⁷ guidelines. Further support is provided by Identifiers.org. Identifiers.org has been providing standardised URIs to the scientific community for over a decade^{28,29}; the system consists of a resolver at its core, but combines a number of other useful facilities. For example,

²⁵ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>

²⁶ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols>

²⁷ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/28662064>

²⁸ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18078503>

²⁹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/22140103>

Identifiers.org records all known resource specific access URLs for a given scientific record, as well as document alternative URI schemes through which datasets can be accessed. This information is crucial for integration activities, as it allows numerous, but equivalent, URIs and URLs to be considered as a single (Identifiers.org as the canonical URI) lexical string. This ‘mapping’ feature is integral to the EMBL-EBI RDF platform³⁰, where Identifiers.org URIs act as a semantic glue in distributed queries. For new data elements, managers of a data source may consider generating their own identifiers. Generating new identifiers is supported by the FAIRifier tool. These are formed as URIs, but may or may not be proper globally unique and resolvable identifiers that can be published on the web. This could be a temporary step, before mapping these provisional (or internal) identifiers to authoritative identifiers, or a manager decides to become the authoritative source (e.g. OrphaCodes from OrphaNet). We advise to consult with other FAIR experts in these cases.

In parallel with the FAIR principles, the JDDCP (Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles) were released in 2014³¹. These provide a set of guiding principles for the publishing of research objects, targeted particularly to scholarly literature. These too advocate the use of global persistent identifiers, but Principle 2 (‘Credit and Attribution’) is concerned with giving credit to individual data providers/databases. To address this, Identifiers.org has recently been extended to allow such attribution, through the compact identifier system³². This style of referencing is specifically targeted to scientific publications, and has already begun to be adopted³³. It provides a simple (easy to use for scientists and publishers) guide for users, whilst retaining the full functionality and richness of the Identifiers.org URI system.

A1.5. Increasing findability through BioSchema’s

In steps 4 and 5 of the FAIRification steps, Bioschemas were briefly introduced as a means to increase findability of resources that provide a web interface for their data. Here, we elaborate on this potentially powerful tool to increase findability of rare disease resources on the web.

Bioschemas is an open community initiative to make life science resources more Findable on the web. Resources are made more Findable, particularly to Web search engines such as Google, by embedding machine readable Schema.org markup in their human facing web pages. The Bioschemas community have developed a collection of profiles over Schema.org that recommend the properties that are most relevant for a particular resource. For example, the [DataCatalog profile](#) identifies the properties most relevant for a data repository while the [Protein profile](#) identifies the properties most relevant for pages describing a protein. Each Bioschemas profile makes a recommendation of up to six minimal properties, a further set of recommended properties, and then a further set of

³⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24413672>

³¹ <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egykh>

³² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29737976>

³³ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29737977>

more optional properties. For each property, the expected values are given together with an example of the usage of the property.

Bioschemas can be used alongside other mechanisms recommended for making specifically rare disease resources findable, such as registration at OrphaNet, registration at the RD-Connect Biobank and Registry finder, and genomics data submission through the RD-Connect platform. These mechanisms, as well as the FAIR data point metadata editor, support the generation of rich metadata to improve Findability and Reuse, and improve data Interoperability through the use of machine readable data. Bioschemas embeds lightweight machine readable metadata in the human facing web pages to enable indexing by web search engines.

A1.6. Documentation of standard protocol for variant annotation of rare disease genomes

In this section, we focus on a pipeline for standardized *comparability* of rare disease genome data. As the price of whole exome sequencing (WES) and whole genome sequencing (WGS) has dropped steeply in recent years, there has been a move within the clinical genetics community toward use of this technology in aiding, and confirming, diagnosis, particularly with regards to rare disease cases. Massively parallel short-read sequencing on Illumina platforms typically results in the production of 40–400 million reads per exome or genome, respectively. This large volume of reads needs to undergo quality control, before being aligned to a reference genome. These alignments can then be interrogated for variant events, that is, positions where the sample sequenced differs from the reference genome sequence, using a range of bioinformatics tools, depending on the nature of the event of interest. It is essential for rare disease research, where data are relatively sparse, that genomics data are comparable. At the same time, as genomics tool development and improvement remains a very active area of research, it is essential to keep abreast of the latest developments. Therefore, two alignment tools, BWA-MEM [Li, 2013: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1303.3997>], and GEM3 (Marco-Sola et al., manuscript in preparation), and three popular variant-calling algorithms, FreeBayes [Garrison and Marth, 2012: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1207.3907>], GATK HaplotypeCaller [DePristo et al., 2011: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21478889>], and SAMtools [Li, 2011: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/21903627>] have been analysed and benchmarked to provide documentation on standards protocol for variant analysis and annotation (Figure 8). Results have been published in Laurie et al., Hum Mut, 2016 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27604516>) and used to set up the bioinformatics pipeline of RD-Connect (<https://platform.rd-connect.eu/>). In the RD-Connect platform, data from sequencing experiments submitted by participating research projects is processed with a standard pipeline and made available for online analysis through a user-friendly interface to authorised users. Other project and platforms can benefit from this documentation to setup their genomic analysis pipeline.

Figure 8: Venn diagrams illustrating concordance of variant identification for BWA-MEM alignments. Separate Venn diagrams show the number and percentage of concordant calls for a particular variant type by pipeline for the NIST reliably callable regions, the NIST non-reliably callable but mappable regions, and the NIST non-reliably callable regions. SNVs, single nucleotide variants; Dels, deletions; Ins, insertions. Figure extracted from Laurie et al., Hum Mut 2016 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27604516>).

A1.7. Conclusions

With regard to this EXCELERATE deliverable 8.2 with the goal to document tools for data manipulation and standard conversions in the rare-disease field, we have described the 7-step FAIRification process, which includes 1) defining driving user questions(s), 2) pre-FAIRification analysis, 3) defining semantic model, 4) transforming data records, 5) defining metadata, 6) deploying FAIR data resource, and 7) querying interface or user app. We also describe auxiliary tools and recommendations for this FAIRification process, and the standardization of rare disease variant calling via the RD-Connect Genome-Phenome Analysis Platform.

We conclude with 5 recommendations for future developments in the community of rare disease data managers (stakeholders), based on practical FAIRification experience:

1. Stakeholders should consider building and maintaining capacity on FAIR data stewardship
2. FAIRification, including its required budget, should be incorporated in Data Management Plans. Because of the interdisciplinary nature of FAIRification and the early state of development of support for FAIR data stewards, a DMP typically involves interdisciplinary and cross-organisational collaboration.
3. Institutions are advised to develop an institutional standard for FAIR metadata collection and storage
4. The FAIRification process should start prior to data capture
5. Data models should be shared and reused for record level FAIR data

Future focus for the rare disease community in ELIXIR will be towards improving support specifically for FAIR data stewards working in the rare disease domain.